

CREATION OF THE IMAGE TRAINING MODEL IN SUPERVISED FAST RANDOM FOREST –FRF- ALGORITHM

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The Fast Random Forest (FRF) image processing algorithm, being a machine learning supervised algorithms, allows to create a classifier model (training model) able to detect the same classes (features) in other images. In order to prove the efficiency of the FRF training model [1] it is executed the following test:

1. **Step 1 (Fig.1(a)):** are selected the classes of the training model into the test image (in the analyzed case are selected four main classes corresponding to the three main sub-figures/symbols, named 'features', to detect such as circles, stars, crosses and background);
2. **Step 2 (Fig.1(b)):** is executed the FRF algorithm by identifying the selected classes in the whole image (see the colors of Fig.1(b) corresponding to the defined four classes) thus creating the training model which is saved into the platform system;
3. **Step 3 (Fig. 1(c)):** is loaded the same image (or other similar ones to find the same sub-figures/symbols) by applying the saved classifier of the Step 2 (output of the execution of Fig.1 (b)), but selecting different classes to detect (in the limit case of the proposed test are selected for all the four classes the background and not the shapes to identify);
4. **Step 4 (Fig. 1(d)):** is executed the FRF algorithm by identifying all the four classes as for the Step 2, but by supervising the algorithm selecting regions having not the features to extract (this proves the correct and efficient functioning of the training model).

Figure 1: (a) Test image and selected regions identifying the features to extract. (b) Extracted features corresponding to the four colors (red: class1; green: class2; violet: class 3; brown: class4). (c) Same test image identifying other class regions (background) to prove the correct and efficient functioning of the FRF training model. (d) Extracted features corresponding to the four classes of the training model (the training model addresses the features extraction to the classes of the training model and not to the new wrong classes representing the background).